

Fe(III), Co(III), Cu(II) and Ni(II) Derivatives of Some New Monothio- β -Diketones[†]

S. K. SAINI*, V. D. GUPTA** and R. C. MEHROTRA

Chemical Laboratories, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004

A few new monothio- β -diketones, [RCSCH₂COR', where R = Ph, Me; R' = C₆H₄Cl(p), C₆H₄Br(p), C₆H₄Me(p), C₆H₄OCH₃(p)] have been synthesized and their metal complexes with Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(III) and Fe(III) were prepared. These were characterized by elemental analysis, ir, magnetic measurements, electronic spectra. Molecular weight determination in refluxing chloroform showed them to be monomeric.

REPLACEMENT of an oxygen by a sulphur atom in β -diketones brings about considerable deviation in the properties of derived transition metal complexes^{1,2}. This has led to considerable activity in the field of monothio- β -diketonate derivatives³⁻⁵. We have synthesized a few new monothio- β -diketones [RCSCH₂COC₆H₄X(p); X = Cl, Br, Me or OMe] having chloro, bromo, methyl and methoxy substituents in the phenyl ring. The present paper deals with a number of their transition metal complexes of Fe(III), Co(III), Ni(II), Cu(II).

Experimental

Diethyl ether (Alembic), methanol (BDH) and acetonitrile (BDH) were dried by the standard methods. Benzonitrile and acetophenones were distilled before use. Sodamide (May and Baker) was used as such. Sulphur was estimated gravimetrically as barium sulphate. Nickel, cobalt, copper and iron were estimated by standard methods⁶. Molecular weight was determined by semimicro Gallenkamp Ebulliometer using thermometer sensing in refluxing chloroform. Magnetic measurements were carried out with Gouy's balance at room temperature (303 K). Infrared spectra were recorded in the region 4000-200 cm⁻¹ on Perkin-Elmer Model 577 in nujol mulls using cesium iodide window. Electronic spectra were taken on Beckman DU-26 spectrophotometer in chloroform.

Preparation of monothio- β -diketones⁶: 0.1 mole of substituted acetophenone was added to a stirred ethereal suspension of sodamide (0.2 mole) in a three necked round bottom flask (500 ml) fitted with a dropping funnel, mechanical stirrer and a condenser. After half an hour, an ethereal solution of ethyl thio ester (0.1 mole) was added dropwise with stirring at 0°. The reaction mixture was then stirred for 3-4 hr and was left overnight. The sodium salt of monothio- β -diketone formed was poured in ice-cold water and extracted with solvent ether. The extract was treated with CO₂ to precipitate the monothio- β -diketones. The solid red to yellow product was

filtered, washed with water and then crystallized from ether or ethanol.

Preparation of nickel(II), copper(II) and cobalt(III) monothio- β -diketonate derivatives: A solution of Ni(II) or Cu(II) acetate in aqueous methanol (20 ml) was mixed with aqueous solution of monothio- β -diketone in 1:2 molar ratio. The precipitated complex was filtered, washed with water and crystallized from dry methanol or acetonitrile. For the preparation of Co(III) complexes, Co(II) acetate was reacted with the ligand in acetonitrile (Table 2).

Preparation of iron(III) monothio- β -diketonate derivatives: On addition of aqueous solution of iron(III) chloride to a hot solution of monothio- β -diketones in methanol (1:3 molar ratio), a dark brown compound was precipitated which was filtered, washed with water and crystallized from dry methanol (Table 2).

Results and Discussion

The new monothio- β -diketones were prepared by the following route:

The thione ester can be easily prepared from the corresponding nitrile:

[R = Me or Ph; R' = C₆H₄X(p);
X = Cl, Br, Me or OMe]

All these ligands were prepared in good yields as red and orange solids (Table 1) and were characterized.

[†] Dedicated to Prof. A. K. Dey on his sixtieth birthday.

Present Address: * Scientist, Defence Material & Stores Research & Development Estt., Post Box No. 320, Kanpur-208 013.
** Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi.

TABLE 1—MONOTHIO- β -DIKETONES, $\text{RCSCH}_2\text{COC}_n\text{H}_4\text{X}(p)$ USED IN THE PRESENT WORK

R	X	m.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	S% Found (Calcd.)
Ph	Cl	115	62	11.4 (11.6)
Ph	Br*	129-30	58	9.9 (10.0)
Ph	Me*	124-25	61	12.6 (12.6)
Ph	OMe	121	62	11.8 (11.8)
Me	Cl	38-39	54	15.1 (15.0)
Me	Br	88-89	42	12.4 (12.4)
Me	Me*	67-68	48	16.6 (16.7)
Me	OMe*	56-57	50	15.5 (15.4)

*Reported earlier ; ref. 7.

The ir spectra of these monothio- β -diketones¹⁻³ display characteristic absorptions in the ranges 1585-1600, 1550-1570 and 1240-1260 cm^{-1} due to $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$, $\nu\text{C}=\text{C}$ and $\nu\text{C}-\text{S}$, respectively. In analogy with other thio- β -diketones¹⁻³, these may exist as an equilibrium mixture of tautomeric enol and enethiol forms which interconvert rapidly by the intramolecular chelate proton transfer⁴.

 TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA AND PROPERTIES OF THE TRANSITION METALS MONOTHIO- β -DIKETONATE DERIVATIVES

Metal	R	$\text{C}_n\text{H}_4\text{X}_p$	n	Nature	m.p. (°C)	Metal % Found (Calcd.)	Sulphur % Found (Calcd.)	Mol. Wt. Found (Calcd.)
Ni	Me	CH_3	2	Dark brown solid	216	13.2 (13.3)	14.9 (14.5)	—
Ni	Me	Br	2	Brown solid	224	10.9 (10.3)	11.9 (11.2)	540 (571)
Ni	Ph	OMe	2	Brown solid	208	9.7 (9.8)	10.0 (10.7)	—
Cu	Me	Cl	2	Red brown solid	176	13.3 (13.1)	13.3 (13.2)	460 (487)
Cu	Ph	CH_3	2	Brown solid	193	11.8 (11.15)	11.5 (11.2)	—
Cu	Ph	Br	2	Brown solid	164	9.1 (9.1)	9.6 (9.1)	688 (699)
Cu	Ph	OMe	2	Brown solid	182	10.0 (10.6)	10.8 (10.6)	—
Co	Ph	Br	3	Red brown solid	214	5.5 (5.8)	9.3 (9.5)	1002 (1013)
Co	Ph	Cl	3	Red brown solid	156	6.6 (6.7)	10.8 (10.9)	—
Co	Me	Cl	3	Red solid	164	8.2 (8.5)	13.7 (13.8)	688 (693)
Fe	Ph	Br	3	Dark green solid	178	5.8 (5.5)	9.8 (9.5)	—
Fe	Me	Br	3	Green solid	157	6.2 (6.8)	12.0 (11.7)	—
Fe	Me	Cl	3	Green solid	210	8.3 (8.1)	14.1 (13.9)	692 (690)

A few latter transition metal complexes of the type $\text{M}(\text{RCSCHCOC}_n\text{H}_4\text{X}_p)_n$, ($\text{M}=\text{Fe}$, Co , $n=3$; $\text{M}=\text{Cu}$, Ni ; $n=2$) were synthesized from the corresponding acetate or chloride in methanol or acetonitrile and crystallized from these solvents :

A similar reaction of cobalt(II) acetate led to the synthesis of the *tris* derivatives only due to the oxidation of cobalt(II) to cobalt(III) in aqueous media by the atmospheric oxygen. All the metal complexes were from dark brown to dark red solids with sharp melting points, soluble in chloroform and benzene. Molecular weight determinations, carried out in a few representative cases showed them to be monomeric in refluxing chloroform (Table 2).

The ir spectral characteristics of the transition metal monothio- β -diketonates were consistent with the conjugated chelate structure, in harmony with the observation of previous workers¹⁻³. Of the more significant bands, these metal complexes had two characteristic bands above the 1480 cm^{-1} . The band of higher frequency at 1595-1555 cm^{-1} has been assigned to $\nu\text{C}-\text{O}$ vibrations, while the band of lower frequency at 1516-1490 cm^{-1} was due to $\nu\text{C}-\text{C}$ vibration of phenyl ring. The $\nu\text{C}-\text{S}$ vibration was observed in the region 1235-1255 cm^{-1} . The metal-oxygen and metal-sulphur frequencies could be noted at 440-490 and 345-290 cm^{-1} regions, respectively.

Magnetic susceptibilities of some of the complexes were measured with Gouy's balance (Table 3).

TABLE 3—MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF THE METAL COMPLEXES ;
M(RCSCHCOR)_n

Metal	R	R'	μ_{eff} B.M.
Fe(III)	Me	C ₆ H ₄ Br- <i>p</i>	5.20
Fe(III)	Ph	C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ - <i>p</i>	5.15
Cu(II)	Ph	C ₆ H ₄ Cl- <i>p</i>	2.08
Cu(II)	Me	C ₆ H ₄ Cl- <i>p</i>	1.97
Cu(II)	Ph	C ₆ H ₄ Br- <i>p</i>	1.95
Cu(II)	Ph	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ - <i>p</i>	1.80

The complexes of nickel(II) with these monothio- β -diketones are found to be diamagnetic like other nickel complexes of other monothio- β -diketones⁹. Replacement of one oxygen atom in β -diketone by sulphur causes a change in bond type of the respective nickel(II) complexes from spin free to spin paired. Attempts to prepare cobalt(II) complexes which would be spin paired were unsuccessful. The quick oxidation of cobalt(II) to cobalt(III) also occurs with certain soft bases such as NO₂⁻, CN⁻, etc¹⁰. It is of interest to observe that iron(III) complexes with these ligands are spin free like those with other monothio-diketonates. The thio- β -diketonate complexes of copper(II) were found to have magnetic moments of 1.8-2.0 B.M. indicating the presence of one unpaired electron.

Most of the published work on the electronic spectra of metal complexes of monothio- β -diketones has been reported on the nickel(II) chelates. In the case of nickel complexes reported here, the positions and intensity of the bands [630-640 nm (Md—Md); 520-530 nm (Md—L _{π}); 405-430 nm (L _{π} —Md); 300-338 nm (L _{π} —L _{π})] are in good agreement with the values of other nickel complexes reported in the literature².

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